

CONSIDERATIONS ON THE DESIGNATION OF MOUNTAIN AREAS AS PILLARS OF SUPPORT FOR SOCIETY IN THE CRISIS GENERATED BY CORONAVIRUS

Manuela APETREI

“CE-MONT” Mountain Economy Center of the “Costin C. Kiritescu”
National Institute for Economic Research – INCE, Romanian Academy,
59 Petreni Street, Vatra Dornei, Romania,
sincari_manuela@yahoo.com

Abstract

The lesson we can learn from the Coronavirus crisis is that we need to think long-term and beyond financial risks. The choices we make now must take into account the economic recovery based on considerations that support sustainability. In this scientific approach I started from the hypothesis of designating the mountain area as a pillar of support of society in the crisis generated by Coronavirus. If we look realistically, but from an optimistic perspective, we will see that this crisis has brought to light many opportunities in the mountain area, which have not been given due attention, especially for political reasons. The mountain (as a whole) can support society and the economy. Romania's mountainous area is essential for our well-being and health, whether we are talking about the short-term or the long-term, although it has been less found in the existing policies and in the current decision-making tools and system. In addition to providing us with high-quality mountain products, the water we consume, and the air we breathe, mountain ecosystems (which have not withstood the chemicalization process) also help communities to be more resilient to social and environmental changes.

Keywords: *mountain area, COVID 19, mountain product, forest therapy, mountain tourism.*

INTRODUCTION

The situation generated by COVID-19 surprised us all. Even if the origins of this virus are still debated (ceccar.ro), the health emergency and the resulting global economic crisis warn us that all countries, both developed and least developed, must be better prepared because this new crisis exacerbates existing crises. such as the climate, economic, ecological and demographic crisis.

From an economic point of view, the beginning of the year in Romania was promising. In January, respectively February 2020, the Romanian economy *was in a relatively good state, with a relatively differentiated evolution at sectoral level. In March 2020, at the beginning of the Sars-2-COVID 19 pandemic crisis, the annual inflation remained at 3.05%, a level corresponding to the previous month, February. Only in the food group, more obvious price increases were observed, being conditioned by the seasonal effect for vegetables (+5.43%) and fruits (+ 4.04%), but also by an additional demand (+1.79% for flour, +1.26% for canned meat). The group of non-food products, hygiene items, cosmetics and medicines, registered a marginal increase in prices of only 0.16%, while fuel prices fell by 2.64%. (CNSP Report).*

The new outbreak of coronavirus that generates the disease called COVID-19 has evolved exponentially, shifting rapidly from a local problem to a global crisis (Zhou et al., 2020). The most painful is that we are talking about a human tragedy, the virus affecting hundreds of thousands of people, especially the elderly and comorbidities (Arentz et al., 2020) causing

panic and social instability. In addition to the considerable social impact, we are talking about a growing impact on the global economy. The accentuation of the crisis is determined by its accelerating evolution, which led to the urgent finding and implementation of viable solutions adapted to all levels affected by the amplification of the crisis. It is thus necessary to adopt a new (more rational) behavior, due to significant changes in the structure of economies and market shares of companies (Bonciu, 2020).

Fig. 1. Evolution of the annual inflation rate

Source: CNSP – processing based on INS data

In Romania, after the establishment of the state of emergency, which lasted for a period of two months (March 16-May 15), the COVID-19 epidemic has a strong negative economic impact. Physical distancing (the short- and medium-term solution) has led in many economies to the so-called "shutdown" effect, which is nothing more than the reduction or even partial or total cessation of economic activities to prevent the spread of SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus, which causes COVID-19 disease. Romania is facing a significant contraction in economic activity, requiring rapid and constructive action by all governmental, economic and social actors to limit the immediate and long-term effects of this crisis (Club of Romanian Farmers for Performance Agriculture). The restriction of economic activity immediately results in a reduction in staff and their income. Hence, further declines in demand for products (especially products that do not meet basic needs) that will affect the business chain. Demand also decreased significantly in the case of activities that had a B2C (business to consumer) relationship, with direct sales to the final consumer. Lack of consumption leads to lack of liquidity and for this reason we are spinning in a vicious circle. For the state, this entails additional costs with unemployment and social benefits. The main challenges for short and medium term for local agri-food producers were:

- temporary suspension of the activities of the units from the HORECA network;
- closing shops of traditional products;
- changing the shopping cart (increasing the share of certain products: flour, oil, yeast, sugar – reflecting in some cases an irrational behavior – and limiting the amount of

other products due to isolation at home), but also changing eating habits in situations of medical isolation or quarantine;

- the particularity of the agricultural labor force – the advanced age of the workers in this sector and their vulnerability to the effects of the coronavirus pandemic.

The lack of predictability generated by COVID-19 is far from dispelled, and the consequences on the economies of the world's states are becoming increasingly difficult to estimate. For this reason, competition for financial resources is fierce. In Romania, foreign direct investments are in decline in the first part of 2020, and domestic ones, although slightly recovering compared to previous years, remain insufficient (Finance newspaper, 23.07.2020) to keep the economy afloat.

METHODOLOGY

According to the methodological approach, the research is highlighted by an inter-disciplinary analysis. Starting from the advantages of efficient exploitation of the mountain on the principles of sustainability by capitalizing on mountain products, fresh air, forestry therapy and mountain tourism in all its forms, we ask ourselves whether we can designate mountain areas as pillars of society in exceptional situations such as pandemics.

The present study is considering an x-ray of the concept of mountain area by its relation to a spatial perspective highlighting a series of consequences at a practical level in the coronavirus crisis. In order to achieve the proposed objectives, the following are used as bibliographic and information sources:

- specialized books published in the country and abroad by nationally and internationally recognized authors;
- articles published in national and international databases.

The research methods used in the paper are: documentation, especially theoretical documentation, through the analysis of the literature, in this sense being studied numerous books, studies, national and international articles; statistical methods, such as classification and synthesis and the method of interdisciplinary research, which is based on knowledge from other fields, such as economics (tourism), forestry, sociology, environmental science and medical information.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the conditions of the new pandemic, we are witnessing to the rise of a new "religion": that of SECURITY. Mountain tourism, through its valences, is becoming a viable option given the social distance as the first method to reduce the degree of infection. It is also time to take advantage of the benefits of forest therapy, as a natural therapeutic method by which certain diseases are prevented and cured through trees or the forest as a whole, thanks to forest aerosols. The very good general conditions of the mountain environment (clean air, clean water and the absence of chemicalization), to which are added the extensive animal husbandry systems (in motion, with the elimination of toxins by perspiration), all these components meet on the one hand the ecological conditions, but in addition, to a superior biological quality, especially protein, for mountain products with maximum guarantees for the health of consumers.

Moreover, the economic crisis is coming with a real opportunity for our country, but it must be capitalized on. Perhaps one of the few advantages of this situation is the awareness of the role of the small peasant household in the mountains, which even in exceptional conditions can provide food for household members, but also for the small community to which it belongs. Not to mention the emotional benefits, by the fact that people, by the nature of the activity, managed to enjoy the fresh air, the sun, they managed to keep their minds occupied, without being victims of the gloomy scenario presented daily on TV, scenario which sometimes takes on apocalyptic dimensions. Another advantage is that due to the imposition of social distance, intermediaries between small agricultural producers and consumers have disappeared, in this case small producers have had to look for solutions to capitalize on perishable goods and have had a double benefit: higher profits (the part of intermediaries has reached the producers), but also an increase of confidence in their own powers (generally the capitalization is done directly at the door of the block, based on order by phone or in some cases online).

The mountain (as a whole) can support society and the economy. Romania's mountainous area is essential for our well-being and health, whether we are talking about the short term or the long term. However, the mountain area has been found too little in existing policies and in the current decision-making tools and system. The mountain must benefit from a specific policy defined according to the principles of sustainable development (Rey, 2008) Mountain ecosystems (those well preserved, protected or managed) provide support for high quality mountain products, the water we drink and the air we breathe, helping communities, through a combination of factors, to be more resilient to social and environmental change. In the case of the Romanian mountains, we are talking about a great advantage: the fact that they were not significantly or not at all subjected to the chemicalization process, this offers the highest guarantees of quality and health for consumers, from the beginning (Apetrei, 2017). The geo-climatic characteristics of the Romanian Carpathians, the large areas of natural pastures and pastures for the fertilization of which natural fertilizers are used, the use of unconventional energies, recyclable in exploitation technologies, the fact that the main animals growing in the mountain area (sheep and cattle) it does not enter into direct competition with man through the specific way of feeding (Rey, 2018), represent solid reasons for the efficient exploitation and capitalization of the mountain area.

THE STRENGTHS OF THE MOUNTAIN AREA IN THE CORONAVIRUS CRISIS

The air

During a day, a person consumes about two liters of fluids, a kilogram and a half of food and inhales no less than 19 cubic meters of air (<https://noi.md/md/diverse/de-citicipaci-e-nevoie-pentru-a-asigura-necesarul-de-oxigen-pentru-un-om>). Air is the first and most important vital resource for each of us and it depends on it, more than we can imagine, our health and life. Air, as a major component of the natural environment can affect all aspects of life, as well as human health. Therefore, the transmission of viruses can be influenced by a number of factors, such as pollution and climatic conditions (we must pay special attention to temperature and humidity) (Nasraldin, 2020). In the mountain area the air temperature shows annual and diurnal variations, decreasing depending on the altitude, with about 0.5°C every 100 m, up to 5 km and with 0.7°C from 5–7 km (Rey, 2018). Altitude, as a contributing or inhibitory factor in the spread of the new coronavirus, was taken into account by

researchers. Thus, cases of Covid 19 have been reported in high altitude regions of Europe, Asia, South America, North America and Africa (Arias-Reyes et al., 2020; Huamani et al., 2020; Xi et al., 2020; Zeng et al., 2020). Although cases of Covid 19 have been reported in mountainous regions, the epidemiological analysis provided by Arias-Reyes et al. much lower disease transmission in these areas. Similarly, Xi et al (2020) reported a low incidence of COVID-19 disease on the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau (average altitude 4,785 m, area 2,000,000 km²). Possible reasons for this virus resistance would be:

- physiological adaptation to hypoxia (insufficient supply of oxygen in the tissues);
- environmental factors that support or inhibit viral transmission; (humidity, temperature variations);
- ethnic and genetic differences of populations in different mountain areas;

One aspect that needs to be deepened is the impact of ultraviolet radiation (from a natural source) on organisms, depending on altitude. UV radiation (RUV) is non-ionizing electromagnetic radiation, with a wavelength between 10 and 400 nm (Decean, 2011).

The ultraviolet spectrum is divided, depending on the wavelength measured in nanometers, into 3 spectral bands: ultraviolet C (length 100–280 nm) which are blocked by the ozone layer, ultraviolet B (length 280–315 nm) and ultraviolet A (length of 315–400 that reach the earth and affect the human body, but also objects on earth (cnmrmc.insp.gov.ro, National Institute of Public Health, 2012). Altitude greatly intensifies ultraviolet radiation (RUV). For type A ultraviolet their intensity at 1000 m is 17%, at 2000 m their intensity is 27%, at 3000 m their intensity is 34% and at 5000 m their intensity is 44%, and for type ultraviolet B, the intensity at 1000 m is 20%, the intensity at 2000 m is 35%, at 3000 m it is 50% and at 5000 m it is 70% (Tache, 2000). More UV radiation comes into contact with the earth and organisms (Pun et al., 2020). 254 nm UV is lethal to SARS-CoV-2 and other viruses (Sangripanti and Lytle, 2020). It turns out that sunlight should not cause significant inactivation of SARS-CoV-2, but we are undoubtedly talking about a lower strength of the virus due to type B ultraviolet rays, because they are found in a much higher proportion in the mountains than in the lowlands (Pun et al., 2020). The intensity of UV radiation increases with altitude, as a result of the reduction of the atmospheric layer that participates in the absorption of radiation (cnmrmc.insp.gov.ro, National Institute of Public Health, 2012). Thus, UV radiation could help slow the spread of the virus as some researchers have suggested (Cadnum et al., 2020; Hamzavi et al., 2020; Keil et al., 2020), but this needs to be further examined. Regarding temperature, scientific studies have not yet reached a consensus on the direct causal relationship between air temperature and the degree of spread of the virus (Yao et al., 2020).

In terms of pollution, the relationship is simple: the more pollution the more diseases (Pansini and Fornacca, 2020; Setti et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2020), because airborne pathogens are partially subject to air pollutants (Merow and Urban, 2020). These viruses can bind to airborne particles; this interaction helps them stay in the air longer, favoring their inhalation, which leads to severe respiratory symptoms, increasing health complications even leading to death (Rabbi et al., 2020). Prolonged exposure to air pollution is a well-known cause of inflammation, which has the effect of hyperactivating the innate immune system, even in healthy young subjects. Thus, those living in areas with high levels of pollutants are more prone to the development of chronic respiratory diseases being much more vulnerable to any new infectious agent (Conticini et al., 2020).

Air pollution is a contributing factor to the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus (Brandt et al., 2020; Fattorini and Regoli, 2020) and in general, many mountainous areas have less to do with pollution related to industry and automobiles (Pun et al., 2020). Pollution in the mountain area is generated mainly by the burning of biomass for heating and cooking (Thakur et al., 2020), the peculiarities related to the urban model (Vert, 2000) of the agglomeration (urban metropolis developed on the matrix of a medieval settlement, with streets narrow, see the city of Brasov (**45°39'N 25°36'E**)), by episodes of thermal inversion (when a layer of cold air accumulates under a layer of warm air, and the layer of thermal inversion acts as a cover that prevents the dispersion and transport of pollutants). The rapid spread of SARS-CoV-2 infection, seen in many countries around the world, could be linked to years of exposure to poor air quality, which over time impairs the health of the community in affected areas (Suhaimi et al., 2020). For this reason, special attention is required in the direction of identifying corrective solutions, so that all these negative effects of anthropogenic activities are greatly diminished so that the mountain remains, as it has been for centuries, a source of health.

Forest therapy

Forest therapy is that natural therapeutic method by which certain diseases are prevented and cured through trees or the forest as a whole due to forest aerosols (Devadason, et al. 2008). A mountain aerosol bath involves a walk in the woods for relaxation and recreation while inhaling substances emanating from trees (Quiq, 2009) called phytoncides which are volatile antimicrobial organic compounds (Nakadai et al., 2006). Forest aerosols are particles of volatile oil on which a thin film of water condenses, and this mixture acquires an electric charge with a dynamizing effect. Aeroionization, which represents the content of subatomic particles in the atmosphere is extremely beneficial to organisms especially in conditions of prevalence of positive ions (Ciangă, 2009). The air we breathe contains positive or negative ions (due to the different number of electrons on the last layer). While positive ions occur as a result of industrial processes and pollution, strong negative ionized air is found in the upper part of forest-covered mountain slopes, near waterfalls and waterfalls formed by rivers and streams mountain. In the production of negative ions, naturally, several factors participate: ultraviolet radiation that is very strong in the mountain area (Pun et al., 2020), rain, waterfalls and waterfalls, the process of photosynthesis and cold winds that cross the softwood forests. The lifespan of these ions is very short, only 1 minute and they have been called air vitamins, because they have a stimulating and harmonizing impact on all vital processes, but also on the psyche and mental. The immune system is extremely active in the presence of these ions (Quiq, 2009) blood circulation intensifies and regeneration processes are stimulated. On the high mountain ridges, especially where there are fir forests, near the waterfalls and cataracts made by the mountain streams, the concentration of negative ions increases up to 4,000/cm³, while in the University Square in Bucharest (**44°26'7"N 26°6'10"E**), the concentration theirs is only 100/cm³ 40 times smaller (touchesorganic.ro). When we are in the presence of negative ions, we tend to be in a good mood, with a more intense and much more attentive mental creativity (Morita et al., 2007). Recreation in green spaces such as parks and forests has substantial health benefits (Kahlmeier et al. 2014) and is more important for mental health benefits than recreation in gray urban areas (Fong et al. 2018).

On the contrary, in the presence of positive ions (whose concentration is high in the plain areas without vegetation and in the mountain depressions) the power of concentration decreases, there are headaches, malaise, drowsiness, various nervous disorders (Kusaka et al., 1992).

The importance of mountain aerosols lies in the fact that one of the most sterile environments is found in the middle of a forest. Thus, forests are not the favorable environment for the development of microbes in general, as evidenced by the results of experimental research showing that in a cubic meter of air in the forest there are only about 5–500 microbial germs, while: in a hospital are from 10,000 microbes (in the happiest cases); up to 20,000 microbes can be found in homes; up to 5,000,000 microbes are found in an office, and up to 9,000,000 microbial germs in a hypermarket (Paraschiv, 2003). People suffering from chronic or recurrent respiratory diseases, such as pneumonia, bronchitis, pulmonary tuberculosis, tonsillitis, infectious rhinitis, should be treated with forest aerosols every summer.

The mountain product

The natural handicaps specific to the mountain area generated by the physical-geographical conditions, altitude, terrain slope, vegetation period had as effect the inability to develop intensive agriculture (characterized by high productivity supported by the widespread use of chemical fertilizers) and the development of extensive agriculture, agriculture friendly with nature (Rey, 2008), which results in natural products with a high quality level from a sanogenic point of view. The mountain product is one of the most important resources in the mountain area, a resource that can be seen both from an economic point of view (because it can be the key to relaunching mountain agriculture), but also from a prophylactic point of view, because the value of mountain products is special in quality, being foods with a very high nutritional value, tasty, healthy, unpolluted and uncontaminated, coming from plants that live in a clean, free and quiet environment, blessed with solar energy, water, air and animals that it benefits from the best quality fodder from mountain meadows with high natural value. *As the altitude increases, the temperature, atmospheric pressure, the amount of oxygen, but also the pollution decreases, which stimulates the metabolism of plants and animals, having the effect of increasing the bioactive substances with the role of defense and adaptation that bring additional qualitative energy value nutritious and sanogenic for agri-food products obtained under the conditions specific to the mountain area* (Gruia et al., 2017). Through its natural valences, through the stored energy value, the mountain food product transforms the most valuable natural elements: soil, pure water, clean air into products with a high quality level. In March 2020, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) developed a mini-guide that can be downloaded from the website with guidelines on food for the population during this period: *good nutrition is very important before, in time and after an infection. Infections have negative effects especially when they cause fever. Under these conditions the body needs extra energy and nutrients. Therefore, maintaining a healthy diet is very important during the COVID-19 pandemic. While there are no foods or dietary supplements that can prevent COVID-19 infection, maintaining a healthy diet is an important part of supporting a strong immune system* (<http://www.fao.org/3/ca8380en/ca8380en.pdf>).

Value-added products for health and the environment, such as mountain products, become competitive on the market only if the consumer understands the benefits of these products.

Mountain tourism

In the same guide developed by FAO in March, physical distance and proper hygiene are the best methods of protection against COVID-19. In high altitude communities, population density is lower compared to plain areas (Cohen and Small, 1998). The higher the concentration of people in a community, the greater the potential for the spread of diseases through contact and proximity (Connolly et al., 2020). Villages and cities at higher altitudes are often remote, difficult to reach, especially in the restrictive travel conditions of a global pandemic. Low population density and remoteness may have played a key role in keeping COVID-19 at bay in these regions, where physical distancing is more of an extension of daily life than a condition imposed by the new context (Pun et al. 2020).

The current situation is unprecedented. In a few months, I witnessed the phenomenon of over-tourism (Dodds & Butler, 2019) to the phenomenon of nontourism, vividly illustrated by blogs and newspaper articles featuring popular tourist sites with "before" and "after" photos (Condé Nast Traveler, 2020). Certainly 2020 will not be a good year for holidays too far from home, but that does not mean we cannot enjoy a safe holiday. The only condition is to strictly observe the measures of physical distance, a condition that can be easily met by practicing mountain tourism in all its forms (mountain hiking, climbing and mountaineering, paragliding, ski tour, extreme skiing, river rafting, horseback riding, mountain biking, Tyrolean).

CONCLUSIONS

One lesson we can learn from this period is that we need to think long-term and beyond financial risks. We need to change our lifestyle and move towards an economic recovery that supports sustainability. The choices we make now can improve or worsen the condition of our planet. Small family farms in the mountain area represent an economic security mechanism and a way of protection in the mountain area. Economic protection, implicitly social protection, is against poverty, ensuring a minimum level of food and earnings. The general, very good conditions of the mountain environment (clean air, clean waters and the absence of chemicalization), to which are added the extensive animal husbandry systems (in motion, with the elimination of toxins by perspiration), all these components meet on the one hand the conditions ecological, but in addition to a superior biological quality of mountain products, especially protein, with maximum guarantees for the health of consumers.

REFERENCES

Articles and books

- Apetrei M, Surdu I.** 2017. Mountain natural heritage, the foundation of cultural diversity and the identity of mountain communities, Journal of Montanology, Vol. XVII.
- Arentz M, Yim E, Klaff L.** 2020. Characteristics and Outcomes of 21 Critically Ill Patients With COVID-19 in Washington State, *JAMA*.

- Arias-Reyes C, Zubieta-DeUrioste N, Poma-Machicao L, Aliaga-Raduan F, Carvajal-Rodriguez F, Dutschmann M, Schneider-Gasser EM, Zubieta-Calleja G, and Soliz J.** 2020. Does the pathogenesis of SARS-CoV-2 virus decrease at high-altitude? *Respir Physiol Neurobiol* 277:103443.
- Brandt EB, Beck AF, Mersha TB.** 2020. Air pollution, racial disparities, and COVID-19 mortality, *J Allergy Clin Immunol* [Epub ahead of print]; DOI: 10.1016/j.jaci.2020.04.035.
- Cadnum JL, Li DF, Redmond SN, John AR, Pearlmutter B, Donskey CJ.** 2020. Effectiveness of ultraviolet-C light and a high-level disinfection cabinet for decontamination of N95 respirators, *Pathog Immun* 5, pg.52– pg. 67.
- Ciangă, N.** 2009. The border of Sibiu, the tourist potential, tourist arrangement and capitalization, *Geographia Napocensis*, Year 3, no. 2.
- Cohen JE, Small C.** 1998. Hypsographic demography: The distribution of human population by altitude, *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 95:14009–14014.
- Conde Nast Traveller.** 2020. Before and after: How coronavirus has emptied tourist attractions around the world, Retrieved March 31, 2020, from <https://www.cntravellerme.com/before-and-after-photos-tourist-attractions-during-Coronavirus>
- Connolly, C, Keil, R, Ali, S H.** 2020. Extended urbanisation and the spatialities of infectious disease: Demographic change, infrastructure and governance, *Urban Studies*, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098020910873>, 2020.
- Conticini, E, Frediani, B, Caro, D.** 2020. Can atmospheric pollution be considered a co-factor in extremely high level of SARS-CoV-2 lethality in Northern Italy? *Environ. Pollut.* 114465.
- Decean Hana, Remus Orăsan.** 2011. The influence of ultraviolet radiation on health, *Palestine of the Third Millennium – Civilization and Sport* Vol. 12, no. 4, October-December 2011, 391–393;
- Devadason, Sunalene G, Mark Everard, Peter Le Souëf.** 2008. Aerosol Therapy and Delivery Systems, *Pediatric Respiratory Medicine* (pp.286–298), DOI: 10.1016/B978-032304048-8.50021-9;
- Dodds R, Butler R.** 2019. (Eds.). Overtourism: Issues, realities and solutions, *De Gruyter*.
- Fattorini D, Regoli F.** 2020. Role of the chronic air pollution levels in the Covid-19 outbreak risk in Italy, *Environ Pollut* 264:114732.
- Florin Bonciu,** 2020. Challenges in Designing Economic Strategies for the Post Covid-19 Era, *Global Economic Observer*, Vol 8, nr.1,
- Fong K C, Hart J E and James P.** 2018. A review of epidemiologic studies on greenness and health: Updated literature through 2017, *Curr. Environ. Health Rep.* 5 77–87.
- Gruia Romulus, Radu Rey, Gaceu L.** 2017. Study on geographical indication (GI) for mountain agri-food products, *Journal of Montanology*, Vol XVII, 2017.
- Hamzavi IH, Lyons AB, Kohli I, Narla S, Parks-Miller A, Gelfand JM, Lim HW, and Ozog DM.** 2020. Ultraviolet germicidal irradiation: Possible method for respirator disinfection to facilitate reuse during the COVID-19 pandemic, *J Am Acad Dermatol* 82:1511–1512, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341934532>
- Huamani´ C, Vela´squez L, Montes S, and Miranda-Solis F.** 2020. Propagation by COVID-19 at high altitude: Cusco case, *Respir Physiol Neurobiol* 279:103448.
- Kahlmeier S, Kelly P, Foster C, Götschi T, Cavill N, Dinsdale H, Woodcock J, Schweizer C, Rutter H, Lieb C.** 2014. Health economic assessment tools (HEAT) for walking and for cycling: methodology and user guide: economic assessment of transport infrastructure and policies: 2014 update, (*World Health Organization*) 2014.
- Keil SD, Ragan I, Yonemura S, Hartson L, Dart NK, Bowen R.** 2020. Inactivation of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 in plasma and platelet products using a riboflavin and ultraviolet light-based photochemical treatment, *Vox Sang* [Epub ahead of print]; DOI: 10.1111/vox.12937.

- Kusaka Y, Kondou H, Morimoro K.** 1992. Healthy lifestyles are associated with higher natural killer cell activity, *Prev Med.* 1992;21:602–15, [PubMed].
- Merow, C, Urban, MC.** 2020. Seasonality and uncertainty in COVID-19 growth rates, *medRxiv* 2020.04.19.20071951. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.19.20071951>
- Morita E, Fukuda S, Nagano J, Hamajima N, Yamamoto H, Iwai Y,** „Psychological effects of forest environments on healthy adults: Shinrin-yoku (forest-air bathing, walking) as a possible method of stress reduction”, *Public Health.* 2007;121:54–63. [PubMed]
- Nakadai A, A Li Q, Matsushima H, Miyazaki Y, Krensky AM, Kawada T.** 2006. Phytoncides (wood essential oils) induce human natural killer cell activity, *Immunopharmacol Immunotoxicol*, 2006;28:319–33; [PubMed].
- Nasraddin Hemin M Amin, Nasraddin Hero M Amin.** 2020. Climate Analysis to Predict Potential Spread and Seasonality for Global (COVID-19) in Iraqi Kurdistan Region. *Kurdistan Journal of Applied Research* (KJAR) Print-ISSN: 2411-7684 | Electronic-ISSN: 2411-7706.
- Pansini, R, Fornacca, D.** 2020. Initial evidence of higher morbidity and mortality due to SARS-CoV-2 in regions with lower air quality. *MedRxiv* 2020.04.04.20053595. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.04.04.20053595>.
- Paraschiv Claudius Marian.** 2003. Treatise for the natural nutrition of the HUMAN, *Christalin Publishing House*, Bucharest.
- Pun Matiram, Rachel Turner, Giacomo Strapazzon, Hermann Brugger, Erik R Swenson.** 2020. Lower Incidence of COVID-19 at High Altitude: Facts and Confounders, *HIGH ALTITUDE MEDICINE & BIOLOGY*, 2020, Mary Ann Liebert, Inc. DOI: 10.1089/ham.2020.0114;
- Quiq Li.** 2010. Effect of forest bathing trips on human immune function. *Environ Health Prev Med.* 2010 Jan; 15(1): 9–17, doi: 10.1007/s12199-008-0068-3
- Rabi, FA, Al Zoubi, MS, Kasasbeh, GA, Salameh, DM, Al-Nasser, AD.** 2019. SARS-CoV-2 and coronavirus disease 2019: What we know so far. *Pathogens* 9: 231., <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9030231>
- Rey Radu.** 2018. Mountain agro-zootechnical economy – where to? *Terra Nostra Publishing House*, Iași.
- Sagripanti JL, Lytle CD,**2020. Estimated Inactivation of Coronaviruses by Solar Radiation with Special Reference to COVID-19. *Photochem Photobiol* [Epub ahead of print]; DOI: 10.1111/php.13293.
- Setti L, Passarini F de Gennaro, G Di Gilio, A Palmisani, J Buono, P Fornari, G Perrone, M Piazzalunga, A Barbieri, P Rizzo, E Miani A.** 2020. Evaluation of the potential relationship between particulate matter (PM) pollution and COVID-19 infection spread in Italy. http://www.simaonlus.it/wpsima/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/COVID_19_position-paper_ENG.pdf
- Suhaimi Nur Faseeha, Mohd Talib Latif, Juliana Jalaludin,** 2020. Demystifying A Possible Relationship between COVID-19, Air Quality and Meteorological Factors: Evidence from Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, *Aerosol and Air Quality Research*.
- Tache S.** 2000. Stresul oxidativ în bolile interne, *Ed. Casa Cărții de Știință Cluj-Napoca*.
- Thakur M, Boudewijns EA, Babu GR, Van Schayck OCP,** 2020 Biomass use and COVID-19: A novel concern, *Environ Res* 186:109586.
- Vert, C.** 2000. Geography of population and human settlements, *West University Publishing House*, Timișoara.
- Xi A, Zhuo M, Dai J, Ding Y, Ma X, Ma X, Wang X, Shi L, Bai H, Zheng H, Nuermberger E, Xu J.** 2020 Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of discharged patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 on the Qinghai plateau. *J Med Virol* [Epub ahead of print]; DOI: 10.1002/jmv.26032, 2020.

- Yao Y, Pan J, Liu Z, Meng X, Wang W, Kan H, Wang W.** 2020 No association of COVID-19 transmission with temperature or UV radiation in Chinese cities. *Eur Respir J* 55:2000517, 2020.
- Zeng J, Peng S, Lei Y, Huang J, Guo Y, Zhang X, Huang X, Pu H, Pan L; and COVID-19 Clinical Research Collaborative Group of Sichuan Provincial People's Hospital,** 2020. Clinical and imaging features of COVID-19 patients: Analysis of data from high-altitude areas. *J Infect* 80: pg.34–pg.36.
- Zhou, C, F Su, T Pei, A Zhang, Y Du, B Luo, Z Cao, J Wang, W Yuan, Y Zhu,** 2020. Covid-19: challenges to gis with big data, *Geography and Sustainability*.
- Zhu, Y, Xie, J, Huang, F Cao.** 2020 Association between short-term exposure to air pollution and COVID-19 infection: Evidence from China. *Sci. Total Environ.* 727: 138704. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138704>

Web pages

- Coronavirus crisis: Lessons for a more sustainable future; https://ceccar.ro/ro/?page_id=18177, access 08.09.2021
- National Commission for Strategy and Forecast; <http://www.cnp.ro/ro/prognoze>, access 29.09.2020
- Romanian Farmers Club for Performance Agriculture; https://cfro.ro/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/2020-03-27-Letter-Club-Farmers-Romanians_Minister-MADR.pdf, access 06.09.2020;
- Finance newspaper, 23.07.2020; <https://www.zf.ro/opinions/dan-badin-partner-services-fiscal-deloitte-romania-crisis-generated-19437069>, access 13.09.2020
- Guidance on recommendations for the population to protect against exposure to natural and artificial ultraviolet (UV) radiation; <https://cnmrmc.insp.gov.ro/cnmrmc/images/ghiduri/Ghid-Radiatii-Ultraviolete.pdf>, access 07.09.2021
- You are what you breathe; <https://atingeorganic.ro/ro/blogs/news/113058499-rejuvenation-week-ziua-2-e-ti- ceea-ce-respiri>, access 13.10.2021
- Maintaining a healthy diet during the COVID-19 pandemic; <http://www.fao.org/3/ca8380en/ca8380en.pdf>, access 11.10.2020
- <https://noi.md/md/diverse/de-citi-copaci-e-nevoie-pentru-a-asigura-necesarul-de-oxigen-pentru-un-om>, access 07.09.2020.

Projects and studies

- CNSP Report – National Strategy and Forecast Commission
Project “Sustainable mountain strategy”, Radu Rey, Gheorghe Ionașcu, 2008;